

Kinetics of Oxidation of Primary Alcohols by Acid Bromate

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The kinetics of oxidation of primary alcohols by acid bromate has been studied in acetic acid-water medium in presence of sulphuric acid. Order with respect to oxidant was one and fractional with respect to substrate. The order of reacting alcohols is not regular and does not show correlation with Taft plot. Decomposition constants for the alcohol-bromate complexes were calculated and the plot of $\log k_d$ versus Taft σ^* values gave a linear plot with a slope of -0.70 indicating the formation of a transition state with small positive charge on α -carbon atom.

OXIDATION of several aliphatic, aromatic, primary and secondary alcohols and also alicyclic alcohols have been studied in detail by using different oxidants like Ce(IV)¹⁻⁴, Cr(VI)^{5,6} and Br₂⁷. Oxidation of secondary alcohols by pure bromate was studied by Venkatasubramanian⁸ *et al*, where they used mercuric acetate for complexing the product Br⁻ ion. Though bromate is a powerful oxidising agent in acid medium, it was used as a source of bromine in presence of Br⁻ ion. In the studies of bromate oxidation, the product Br⁻ ion formed in the reaction mixture reacts with Br(V) to generate bromine which on accumulation oxidises the substrate along with bromate ion. Hence to eliminate the bromine oxidation which is much faster than the oxidation by bromate ion, the product bromide ion, should be suitably complexed as soon as it is formed. This was achieved by using mercuric acetate.

In continuation of our earlier work⁹ on the oxidation of phenols by bromate, we are communicating in this report the results of bromate oxidation of several primary alcohols, at various temperatures in the range 30-60° and in various amounts of acetic acid as solvent.

Experimental

Potassium bromate, (AnalaR, BDH) mercuric acetate (SM) samples were used as such. All the alcohols used were distilled collecting the required fractions. Acetic acid was purified by distillation. The oxidation of alcohols was studied in acid medium in 40% acetic acid and in the presence of mercuric acetate and sulphuric acid in the temperature range 30-60°. The experimental details are given in our earlier paper⁹. Mercuric acetate did not interfere in the oxidation reaction. The mercuric acetate was used as complexing agent to remove Br⁻ ions as HgBr₄²⁻ as soon as they are formed. All the alcohols were oxidised to their corresponding aldehydes which were identified by the melting points of their 2, 4-D.N.P. derivatives.

Results and Discussion

The order with respect to the oxidant was found to be unity which is evident from the plots of $\log(a-x)$ versus time. Experiments were done with different initial concentrations of bromate and the pseudo-first order rate constants were independent of the initial concentration of bromate. A break in the first order plot was observed in the absence of mercuric acetate at the low concentration of sulphuric acid (0.05M) indicating slow bromate oxidation followed by fast bromine oxidation (Fig. 1). In presence of mercuric acetate the break disappeared and a linear plot was obtained. The rate constant

Fig. 1. Plots of $\log(a-x)$ versus time

$[\text{BrO}_3^-] = 5 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[\text{Methanol}] = 5 \times 10^{-2} M$, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 0.05 M$
Acetic acid = 40%, temperature = 45°C
(A) In the presence of Mercuric acetate.
(B) In the absence of Mercuric acetate.

obtained here was equal to the rate constant obtained from the first part of the plot prior to the break. We have conducted the oxidation of alcohols by bromate at 0.5M H₂SO₄ and 40% (v/v) acetic acid, without mercuric acetate. Here we never observed the break in the first order plot, though we observed the yellow colour due to bromine. The liberated bromine does not oxidise the substrate under these conditions whereas at 0.05M H₂SO₄ and 40% acetic acid the oxidation by bromine was evident. This indicates that the oxidation by bromine is suppressed at higher acid concentrations. When the experiment was repeated with mercuric acetate, same rate constant was obtained but no yellow colour due to free bromine was developed. The suppression of bromine oxidation at higher concentration of acid and at higher percentage of acetic acid was also observed in the oxidation of benzaldehydes¹⁰ by bromine and also in the oxidation of hydroxy acids¹¹ by bromine, the rate of oxidation decreased on increasing sulphuric acid concentration and percentage of acetic acid.

The rate of oxidation of alcohols by bromate increases on increasing the concentration of sulphuric acid (Table 1). Plots of log k_{obs} versus log [H₂SO₄] gave linear graph, the gradients of which were different for different alcohols, the values being in the range 1.3 to 1.9, thus showing that the dependence on [H⁺] is not simple.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF SULPHURIC ACID ON THE RATE OF REACTION

Conc. of H ₂ SO ₄ Substrate	k × 10 ³ litres mol ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹				
	0.20	0.40	0.60	0.80	1.00
Methanol	4.01	6.98	13.92	23.28	29.52
Ethanol	0.95	2.56	4.65	6.61	8.84
<i>n</i> -Propanol	1.47	3.31	7.89	11.39	15.78
<i>n</i> -Butanol	0.80	1.97	3.73	7.33	11.39
<i>iso</i> -butanol	1.28	2.92	6.10	9.64	14.40
<i>n</i> -Pentanol	1.67	3.16	7.31	9.84	16.99
<i>iso</i> -pentanol	1.22	3.20	6.03	7.89	12.53
<i>n</i> -Hexanol	1.09	3.65	6.94	13.01	21.93
<i>n</i> -Heptanol	1.36	3.45	6.99	9.43	13.95
Benzyl alcohol	0.90	2.33	4.58	7.89	12.82
2-Phenyl ethyl alcohol	1.03	2.78	4.66	7.12	11.39
2-Cl-Ethanol	0.41	0.97	2.13	3.41	6.40

The reaction was studied at different concentrations of substrate. The slopes of log k_{obs} versus log (alcohols) were not strictly unity. The data also yielded linear plots of 1/k_{obs} versus 1/[ROH] with definite intercept, for all the alcohols studied, suggesting a rate expression of the type.

$$\frac{-d[\text{Br(V)}]}{dt} = \frac{k_d K[\text{ROH}][\text{Br(V)}]}{1 + K[\text{ROH}]}$$

where K is the equilibrium constant for the formation of alcohol-Br(V) complex, and k_d is the

decomposition constant of the alcohol-Br(V) complex. From the plots of 1/k_{obs} versus 1/[ROH] the decomposition constants were calculated.

The reactions were studied with different percentages (v/v) of acetic acid, and linear plots were obtained on plotting log k_{obs} versus 1/D with a positive slope indicating the reaction to be of ion-dipole. The positive ion should be the protonated bromate ion. According to Amis¹² equation, the distance of closest approach (r) of the reactants were calculated from the slopes, assuming the ion to be uni-positive ion, for all the alcohols. The r values obtained were in the ranges of 0.5 to 1.0 Å.

The oxidation was studied in the temperature range 30 to 60° and the thermodynamic parameters were calculated (Table 2). The more negative ΔS[‡] values indicate the rigid activated complex formation.

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS

Substrate	k _{obs} × 10 ³ (l m ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	ΔE [‡]	ΔH [‡]	ΔS [‡]
		K. Joules mol ⁻¹	K. Joules mol ⁻¹	Joules mol ⁻¹ degrees ⁻¹
Methanol	3.84	76.62	73.98	-59.00
Ethanol	0.66	69.67	67.03	-95.00
<i>n</i> -Propanol	1.07	56.11	53.47	-134.00
<i>n</i> -Butanol	0.92	63.85	61.21	—
<i>iso</i> -butanol	1.28	63.22	59.28	—
<i>n</i> -Pentanol	1.03	63.85	61.21	—
<i>iso</i> -pentanol	0.95	63.85	61.21	—
<i>n</i> -Hexanol	1.24	53.26	50.92	—
<i>n</i> -Heptanol	1.17	52.34	49.70	—
Benzyl alcohol	0.63	57.49	54.85	—
2-Phenyl ethyl alcohol	1.07	60.34	57.70	—
2-Cl-ethanol	0.31	81.31	78.67	-65.00

Basing on the experimental facts the possible mechanism was proposed (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

From this mechanism the rate expression was derived in terms of total bromate concentration.

The rate expression obtained was,

$$-\frac{d[\text{BrO}_3^-]}{dt} = \frac{K_1 K_2 k_3 [\text{BrO}_3^-] [\text{H}^+]^2 [\text{ROH}]}{1 + K_1 [\text{H}^+]^2 + K_1 K_2 [\text{ROH}] [\text{H}^+]^2}$$

which explains the observed experimental facts. The first order rate constant can be given as :

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{K_1 K_2 k_3 [\text{H}^+]^2 [\text{ROH}]}{1 + K_1 [\text{H}^+]^2 + K_1 K_2 [\text{ROH}] [\text{H}^+]^2}$$

When $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ is plotted against $1/[\text{ROH}]$ a straight line will be obtained with an intercept.

$$\text{Intercept} = 1/k_3$$

$$\text{slope} = \frac{1}{K_2 k_3} + \frac{1}{K_1 K_2 k_3 [\text{H}^+]^2}$$

Thus slope is dependent on $[\text{H}^+]$, and a plot of the slopes versus $1/[\text{H}^+]^2$ will give a straight line with

an intercept = $\frac{1}{K_1 k_3}$ and slope = $\frac{1}{K_1 K_2 k_3}$. From

this intercept, slope data K_1 , K_2 and k_3 can be calculated.

The effect of substrate at different $[\text{H}^+]$ was studied for the oxidation of ethanol (Table 3), 2-Chloroethanol and *n*-butanol, and K_1 , K_2 and k_3 were calculated. The K_1 value was found to be $(0.2 \text{ l}^2 \text{m}^{-2})$ for all the three substrates. Using this K_1 value $(0.2 \text{ l}^2 \text{m}^{-2})$ K_2 and k_3 values were calculated for other alcohols.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF $[\text{ETHANOL}]$ ON k_{obs} AT DIFFERENT $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ IN BROMATE ETHANOL REACTION

$[\text{BrO}_3^-] = 5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$; Acetic acid = 40%
 $[\text{Mercuric acetate}] = 0.01 \text{ M}$; temp. = 30°

$[\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}]/\text{M}$	$k \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$ at $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]/\text{M}$			
	0.4	0.6	0.8	1.0
5.0×10^{-2}	7.69	11.80	15.29	20.60
7.5×10^{-2}	13.90	19.60	24.39	32.26
1.0×10^{-1}	19.80	27.03	33.33	43.48
1.5×10^{-1}	26.53	34.48	41.67	52.63

The data obtained for the oxidation of different alcohols shows that there is no correlation between the rate and structure of the alcohols. There is no regular order of reactivity for the alcohols. This type of deviation was also observed in the oxidation of alcohols by Br_2 and Ce(IV) .

The equilibrium constant data for the bromate-alcohol complex formation shows that there is no correlation between the equilibrium constant and the polar nature of the alcohols.

The decomposition constants (k_3) were calculated from intercept of $1/k$ versus $1/[\text{ROH}]$ plot; and the $\log k_3$ was plotted against σ^* for methanol, ethanol, *n*-propanol, *n*-butanol, iso-butanol and 2-phenyl ethanol, a straight line with a slope of -0.70 (ρ^*) was obtained (Fig. 2). The ρ^* value suggests formation of a transition state, with a small carbonium

Fig. 2. Plot of $\log k_3$ versus σ^* for primary alcohols.

- (1) Ethanol (2) *n*-Propanol (3) *n*-Butanol
 (4) Iso-butanol (5) 2-Phenyl ethanol (6) Methanol.

ion character. Deviation was observed for the other alcohols with higher number of carbon atoms. The very high k_3 value for benzyl alcohol can be attributed to the resonance stabilisation of the charge on α -carbon atom which is directly attached to the ring.

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